

Contrastive analysis of form and meaning of reduplication in Madurese and Minangkabau language

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Abstract - Every language has its own uniqueness, sometimes making it challenging for speakers of one language to learn another. This research aims to describe the differences in form and meaning of reduplication between Madurese and Minangkabau languages. It is a qualitative descriptive study. The research data consists of reduplicated words in Madurese and Minangkabau sourced from previous research books. Data collection is conducted through document study method. The data analysis employs intralingual matching method. The results of this research indicate differences in reduplication systems between Madurese and Minangkabau: (a) reduplication in Madurese involves partial repetition, while in Minangkabau, it involves complete repetition; (b) there are 4 classes of words that can undergo reduplication in Madurese, compared to 6 words in Minangkabau; (c) reduplication with affixation in Minangkabau is more complex compared to Madurese; and (d) reduplication in Madurese yields 12 variations in meaning, whereas in Minangkabau, there are 8 variations.

Keywords: contrastive linguistics; Madurese; Minangkabau; morphology; reduplication

1. Introduction

Indonesia is a multilingual country. In addition to using Bahasa Indonesia as the national language, the people in this country also use regional languages. There are many regional languages spoken in Indonesia (Agung et al., 2022; Munawaroh et al., 2022). The data regarding the number of regional languages in Indonesia varies. However, all the data indicates that there are more than 700 regional languages in Indonesia (Alfanda et al., 2023; Huszka et al., 2024; Siregar, 2022). The number of speakers of these regional languages differs. Some regional languages have a small number of speakers, while others have many. Wirachmi (2022) listed five regional languages in Indonesia with the largest number of speakers, two of which are Madurese and Minangkabau.

The Madurese language is the third-largest, with approximately 7.7 million speakers. Meanwhile, the Minangkabau language is the fifth-largest, with around 4.2 million speakers. These two regional languages are spoken in regions that are geographically distant from each other. The Madurese language is mainly spoken on Madura Island and in the former Besuki residency area. In contrast, the Minangkabau language is primarily spoken in West Sumatra.

Despite the geographical distance, speakers of these two regional languages can meet each other today. The Madurese ethnic group (speakers of Madurese) and the Minangkabau ethnic group (speakers of Minangkabau) share the characteristic of being among the most migratory ethnic groups in Indonesia (Masluhah & Suryani, 2022). Many Madurese people migrate to various regions across the country, including West Sumatra. Similarly, many Minangkabau people migrate to various regions, including East Java. Therefore, speakers of these two regional languages will likely come into contact with each other, requiring them to learn the local language of their destination.

Learning the Madurese language for the Minangkabau ethnic group or learning the Minangkabau language for the Madurese ethnic group is not as difficult as learning a foreign language. This is because both regional languages belong to the same language family, namely the Austronesian language family, specifically the Malayo-Polynesian branch (Ermanto, 2017; Mursidi & Bakir, 2021; Nalee et al., 2020; Soniatin & Widyaningsih, 2022). Furthermore, Syamsuddin (2019: 64) mentioned that some words in the Madurese language are similar to those in the Minangkabau language but with different pronunciation patterns. Therefore, these two languages share similarities in several aspects. One such similarity is that both languages undergo morphological processes, including affixation, reduplication, and composition (Moehnilibib et al., 1979: 39; Nio et al., 1979: 10). One of the unique morphological processes is reduplication. Reduplication is a type of morphological process that involves repeating the whole or part of the base form, either with or without changes in vowel or consonant phonemes.

As two distinct languages, the reduplication systems in Madurese and Minangkabau languages naturally differ. This is expected because each language has its own uniqueness, leading to differences between them. These unique characteristics make it challenging for Madurese speakers to learn the Minangkabau language and vice versa. Therefore, this article aims to introduce the reduplication systems of these two regional languages to facilitate learning.

The research question in this study is: what are the forms and meanings of reduplication in the Madurese and Minangkabau languages? Based on this, the study aims to describe the forms and meanings of reduplication in the Madurese and Minangkabau languages. The results of this study are expected to make it easier for Madurese speakers or speakers of other languages to understand and learn the reduplication system of the Minangkabau language, as well as for Minangkabau speakers or speakers of other languages to understand and learn the reduplication system of the Madurese language.

This study falls within the scope of contrastive linguistics. Contrastive linguistics is an approach to analyzing languages by identifying similarities and differences between two or more languages in a synchronic manner (Karimah, 2021; Koptleuova et al., 2022; Misdawati, 2019; Widyastuti & Noersadono, 2022). Furthermore, Tarigan (2021: 218) explains that contrastive linguistics studies focus more on differences, while similarities are not emphasized as they are considered common.

The goal of contrastive analysis is to study the similarities and differences in the structure of two different languages. Several aspects that are the focus of contrastive analysis include phonetics, phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, and even pragmatics, as well as non-linguistics behaviors that shape expressions in a particular language (Indraswari, 2017). Contrastive analysis is useful for facilitating second language teaching and translation (Azisi & Nurfaiza, 2022; Nalendra et al., 2021; Qistifani, 2019).

James states that there are two approaches in contrastive linguistics studies, namely applied contrastive analysis and pure contrastive analysis (Nur, 2016). Applied contrastive analysis involves comparing two languages with the aim of solving practical language teaching problems. Meanwhile, pure contrastive analysis refers to the comparison of two languages with a focus on language typology studies, which describe languages based on the dominant features or types in those languages. This study will focus on the applied contrastive analysis approach.

Previous studies relevant to this research have been conducted by several parties. First, Putri (2017) studied reduplication in Javanese and Indonesian. The study found that the forms of reduplication in Javanese and Indonesian have similarities, such as sound-altering reduplication, partial reduplication, full reduplication, affixed reduplication, trilingua, and pseudo-reduplication. These types of reduplication convey various meanings, such as plurality in both quantitative and qualitative terms, actions done casually, recklessly, without a specific purpose, and intensity of feelings. Second, Billah et al. (2023) researched reduplication in Arabic and Indonesian. The study found 11 functions of reduplication in Arabic, including serial order, word formation, distribution, emphasis, intensity, supplication, stages, oaths, warnings, subordination, and part of a part. Meanwhile, 16 functions of reduplication were found in Indonesian, including plurality, forming adverbs, concessive clauses, correlative clauses, casual forms, continuity, intensity, not yet occurred, serial order, humility, emphasis, variety, diminutive, quantifiers, reciprocity, and indefiniteness.

Third, Rahardian (2017) studied reduplication in Javanese and Banjar languages. The analysis revealed differences in the use of juncture during the reduplication process of *dwilingga* with suffixes between Javanese and Banjar languages, leading to differences in repetition patterns. There were also differences in the use of juncture in *dwilingga* reduplication with *simulfixes* between Javanese and Banjar languages, although these differences did not affect the repetition pattern. Fourth, Susetya et al. (2020) studied reduplication in the Madurese language dialect of Probolinggo. The study found various forms of reduplication in Madurese, including sound-altering reduplication, partial reduplication, affixed reduplication, and full reduplication, particularly in casual conversations. Fifth, Afria & Putri (2022) studied reduplication in the Minangkabau language in Kurnia Koto Salak Village, Sungai Rumbai Subdistrict. The study revealed that reduplication in the Minangkabau language includes reduplicated forms for nouns, verbs, and adjectives. Additionally, three types of meanings were identified in the reduplication: (1) nominal reduplication indicates variation in number and size, (2) verbal reduplication describes intensity of events and actions, and (3) adjectival reduplication expresses states and basic meanings.

From the explanation above, it can be seen that the first to third studies compared the reduplication systems of Javanese and Indonesian, Arabic and Indonesian, and Javanese and Banjar. The fourth study only examined reduplication in the Madurese language, while the fifth study only examined reduplication in the Minangkabau language without contrasting it with another language. Based on this literature review, it can be concluded that the novelty of this research, which has not been previously explored by other researchers, is the contrastive analysis of the reduplication systems in the Madurese and Minangkabau languages. Additionally, this study will use data from research conducted by government institutions focused on language studies. As a result, this research is expected to have more comprehensive data, allowing for a more in-depth data analysis.

2. Method

This study employs a descriptive qualitative approach to provide a detailed and systematic analysis of the similarities and differences in the reduplication systems of the Madurese and Minangkabau languages. A qualitative approach is particularly suitable for this research because it allows for an in-depth exploration of linguistic structures and their functions within the respective languages. The primary objective is to describe and compare the forms, meanings, and functions of reduplication in Madurese and Minangkabau.

The data for this research consists of words that undergo the process of reduplication in both languages. These words were selected based on their occurrence in documented linguistic studies. The research was conducted through a literature or document study, meaning that data sources were obtained from existing scholarly works rather than direct field observations. The

main references for this study are research books authored by Sofyan et al. (2008) and Sutawijaya et al. (1984), both of which provide extensive documentation of the grammatical structures of Madurese and Minangkabau.

Data collection was carried out using the observation method, specifically employing the non-participatory observation technique and note-taking technique, as outlined by Azwardi (2018: 103). In this approach, linguistic data were collected by systematically reviewing the selected literature and extracting relevant examples of reduplication. The non-participatory nature of the observation ensured that the study remained objective and focused on the documented linguistic phenomena without researcher intervention.

For data analysis, this study employed the intralingual comparative method, as described by Mahsun (2017). This method involves analyzing linguistic elements within each language independently before comparing them across languages. The primary focus of this comparative analysis was the forms and meanings of reduplication in Madurese and Minangkabau. The analysis was conducted in several stages. First, the various types of reduplication present in each language were identified and classified. Second, the meanings and functions associated with each type of reduplication were examined in their respective linguistic contexts. Third, the similarities and differences in reduplication patterns between the two languages were systematically compared and interpreted.

By employing this structured methodology, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of reduplication in Madurese and Minangkabau. The findings of this research contribute to the broader field of comparative linguistics and provide valuable insights into the morphological processes that shape these two Austronesian languages.

3. Results and Discussion

Every language has its unique characteristics that distinguish it from others. This study aims to describe the reduplication system in the Madurese and Minangkabau languages. After comparing the reduplication systems of Madurese and Minangkabau, it was found that they have notable differences. The following section outlines the reduplication systems of the Madurese and Minangkabau languages in terms of their forms and meanings.

A. Forms of Reduplication in Madurese

In general, reduplication in the Madurese language usually takes the form of partial repetition. Full or complete reduplication is uncommon and may be influenced by other languages. Words that can undergo reduplication in Madurese include nouns, verbs, adjectives, and numerals. The various forms of reduplication in Madurese are detailed below.

a) Initial Syllable Repetition

The first form of reduplication in Madurese involves the repetition of the initial syllable. The partially repeated word is derived from the first syllable of its base form. Words that can be reduplicated in this manner come from specific classes of numerals and nouns. Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>sangá'</i>	<i>sa-sangá'</i>	nine
<i>lakè'</i>	<i>la-lakè'</i>	man
<i>duwâ'</i>	<i>du-duwâ'</i>	two
<i>kabbhi</i>	<i>ka-kabbhi</i>	all

b) Final Syllable Repetition

The second form of reduplication in Madurese involves the repetition of the final syllable. This form of repetition is the most common in the Madurese language. Words that can be reduplicated in this manner include nouns, verbs, adjectives, and numerals. Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>tarètan</i>	<i>tan-tarètan</i>	siblings
<i>bengko</i>	<i>ko-bengko</i>	houses
<i>malâm</i>	<i>lâm-malâm</i>	nights
<i>soko</i>	<i>ko-soko</i>	legs

c) Sound-Altering Repetition

The third form of reduplication in Madurese involves the alteration of vowel phonemes from the base form. This form of reduplication is not widely used in the Madurese language. Words that can undergo sound-altering reduplication are limited, typically involving specific classes of nouns, adjectives, and numerals. Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>rosak</i>	<i>ra-rosak</i>	broken
<i>binè'</i>	<i>ba-binè'</i>	woman
<i>lèma'</i>	<i>la-lèma'</i>	five
<i>ghâlir</i>	<i>lâr-ghâlir</i>	to and fro
<i>pètto'</i>	<i>papètto'</i>	seven

d) Reduplication with Affixation

The fourth form of reduplication in Madurese involves the addition of affixes. The types of affixes used include: i) prefixes, ii) suffixes, and iii) confixes.

i) Reduplication with Prefixes

Prefixes used in Madurese reduplication include *a-*, *ma-*, *ta-*, *pa-*, and *èpa-*. Words that can undergo reduplication with the *a-* prefix include nouns and verbs. Words that can undergo reduplication with the *ma-* prefix include verbs and adjectives. Words that can undergo reduplication with the *ta-* prefix include verbs. Words that can undergo reduplication with the *pa-* and *èpa-* prefixes include adjectives. Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>cangka</i>	<i>aka-cangka</i>	branching
<i>budu'</i>	<i>adu'-budu'</i>	prolific
<i>ghâru</i>	<i>aru-ghâru</i>	scratching
<i>sompa</i>	<i>apa-sompa</i>	swearing repeatedly
<i>berka'</i>	<i>aka'-berka'</i>	running around

Examples of reduplication with the *ma-* prefix:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>sakè'</i>	<i>kè'-masakè'</i>	pretending to be sick
<i>seddhi</i>	<i>dhi-maseddhi</i>	pretending to be sad
<i>pènter</i>	<i>ter-mapènter</i>	acting smart
<i>lapar</i>	<i>par-malapar</i>	acting hungry
<i>soghi</i>	<i>ghi-masoghi</i>	pretending to be rich

Examples of reduplication with the *ta-* prefix:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>tandung</i>	<i>dung-tatandung</i>	stumbling repeatedly
<i>labu</i>	<i>bu-talabu</i>	falling repeatedly
<i>bhentor</i>	<i>tor-tabhentor</i>	colliding repeatedly
<i>toju'</i>	<i>ju'-matoju'</i>	sitting repeatedly
<i>tèdung</i>	<i>dung-tatèdung</i>	stumbling repeatedly

Examples of reduplication with the *pa-* prefix:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>rajâ</i>	<i>pajâ-rajâ</i>	making them big
<i>kènè'</i>	<i>panè'-kènè'</i>	making them small
<i>kandhel</i>	<i>padhel-kandhel</i>	making them thick
<i>jhubâ'</i>	<i>pabâ'-jhubâ'</i>	making them ugly
<i>bhâghus</i>	<i>paghus-bhâghus</i>	making them nice

Examples of reduplication with the *èpa-* prefix:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>rajâ</i>	<i>èpajâ-rajâ</i>	being made big
<i>kandhel</i>	<i>èpadhel-kandhel</i>	being made thick
<i>kènè'</i>	<i>èpanè'-kènè'</i>	being made small
<i>tèpès</i>	<i>èpapès-tèpès</i>	being made thin
<i>bhâghus</i>	<i>èpaghus-bhâghus</i>	being made nice

ii) Reduplication with Suffixes

The suffix used in Madurese reduplication is *-an*. Words that can undergo reduplication with the *-an* suffix include nouns, verbs, and adjectives. Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>lèbâr</i>	<i>bâr-lèbârân</i>	widest
<i>bhâghus</i>	<i>ghus-bhâghusân</i>	best
<i>labu</i>	<i>bu-labuân</i>	falling repeatedly
<i>potè</i>	<i>tè-potean</i>	whitest
<i>ajâm</i>	<i>jâm-ajâman</i>	something resembling a chicken

iii) Reduplication with Confixes

Confixes used in Madurese reduplication include *(N)-aghi* and *pa-aghi*. Words that can undergo reduplication with the *(N)-aghi* confix are verbs, while those with the *pa-aghi* confix are adjectives. Examples of reduplication with the *(N)-aghi* confix:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>tolès</i>	<i>lès-nolèsaghi</i>	writing repeatedly
<i>pokol</i>	<i>kol-mokolaghi</i>	hitting repeatedly
<i>kerra'</i>	<i>ra'-ngerra'aghi</i>	cutting repeatedly
<i>ongghâ</i>	<i>ghâ-ongghâaghi</i>	raising repeatedly
<i>bhâghi</i>	<i>ghi-mâghiaghi</i>	giving repeatedly

Examples of reduplication with the *pa-aghi* confix:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>khènde'</i>	<i>pade'-khènde'aghi</i>	please make them short
<i>lanjhâng</i>	<i>pajhâng-lanjhângaghi</i>	please make them long
<i>tèngghi</i>	<i>paghi-tènggiaghi</i>	please make them tall
<i>jhubâ'</i>	<i>pabâ'-jhubâaghi</i>	please make them ugly
<i>tajhem</i>	<i>pajhem-tajhemaghi</i>	please make them sharp

B. The Meanings of Reduplication in Madurese

Reduplication in Madurese is highly productive and widely used in everyday speech. Different forms of reduplication result in different meanings. In Madurese, reduplication carries various meanings as follows:

a) Stylistic Variation

The first meaning of reduplication is simply for stylistic variation. In this case, the reduplicated word does not acquire a new meaning compared to its base form. This meaning applies to certain nouns and numerals. For example, *lalakè* ('man') retains the same meaning as its base form *lakè*, and *lalèma* ('five') has the same meaning as its base form *lèma*.

b) Plurality

The second meaning of reduplication is to indicate plurality. This meaning is commonly found in Madurese. It applies to nouns, certain verbs, and adjectives when the final syllable of the base form is repeated. Examples include *to-bâto* ('stones'), *bhu-robhhu* ('many who fell down'), and *nè'-kènè* ('many small ones').

c) Resemblance

The third meaning of reduplication indicates resemblance to something else. This meaning applies to nouns that undergo reduplication with the suffix *-an*. Examples include *na'-ana'an* ('something resembling a child') and *jâm-ajâman* ('something resembling a chicken').

d) Repetition

The fourth meaning of reduplication refers to actions performed repeatedly. This meaning applies to nouns and verbs that undergo reduplication with the prefix *a-*, as in *aka-cangka* ('branching repeatedly') and *apa-sompa* ('swearing repeatedly'). It also applies to verbs with final syllable reduplication, like *ghu-nèngghu* ('looking around'), verbs with the prefix *ta-*, such as *butalabu* ('falling repeatedly'), and verbs with the suffix *-an*, like *lok-ologhân* ('calling repeatedly').

e) Pretending

The fifth meaning of reduplication is to express actions performed in pretension. This meaning applies to verbs and adjectives that undergo reduplication with the prefix *ma-*. Examples include *kè'-masakè* ('pretending to be sick') and *neng-masenneng* ('pretending to be happy').

f) Trivial or Playful Actions

The sixth meaning of reduplication refers to actions done in a trivial, aimless, or playful manner. This meaning applies to verbs that undergo reduplication with the suffix *-an* or the confix *(N)-aghi*. Examples include *dung-tèdungan* ('lying down playfully') and *kol-mokolaghi* ('hitting playfully'). Additionally, reduplication with the suffix *-an* indicates actions performed casually or without purpose, as in *kol-tokolan* ('hitting aimlessly') and *lès-tolèsan* ('writing aimlessly').

g) Instruments

The seventh meaning of reduplication indicates tools or instruments used to perform an action. This meaning applies to verbs with final syllable reduplication. Examples include *bhu-tabbhu* ('a beating tool') and *kol-pokol* ('a hitting tool').

h) Hope

The eighth meaning of reduplication expresses hope. This meaning applies to verbs with final syllable reduplication and the addition of the particle *ma' ta'*. Examples include *ma' ta' teng-dâteng* ('wishing they would arrive') and *ma' ta' lè-molè* ('wishing they would return').

i) Commands

The ninth meaning of reduplication is to issue commands to the listener. This meaning applies to verbs with final syllable reduplication, such as *la'-kala'* ('take it') and *kan-ngakan* ('eat it'). It also applies to adjectives with the prefix *pa-* or the confix *pa-aghi*, such as *papès-tèpès* ('make it thin') and *papès-tèpèsaghi* ('please make it thin').

j) Superlative

The tenth meaning of reduplication forms the superlative. This meaning applies to adjectives with the suffix *-an*. Examples include *ghi-soghiân* ('wealthiest') and *jâ-rajâan* ('biggest').

k) Object Focus

The eleventh meaning of reduplication is to focus or emphasize the object. This meaning applies to certain verbs with the suffix *-an*. Examples include *bân-ghibân* ('something that is carried') and *lin-bellin* ('something that is bought').

l) Expression of Amazement

The twelfth meaning of reduplication is to express amazement or surprise. This meaning applies to adjectives with the addition of the emphatic particle *cè'* and the suffix *-na*. Examples include *cè' po-lempona* ('how fat it is') and *cè' nè'-kènè'na* ('how small it is').

m) Reciprocal Actions

The thirteenth meaning of reduplication expresses reciprocal actions. This meaning applies to certain verbs with the suffix *-an*. Examples include *bâs-abâsân* ('mutual looking at each other') and *rè'-tarè'an* ('mutual pulling at each other').

C. Forms of Reduplication in Minangkabau Language

In general, reduplication in the Minangkabau language takes the form of full reduplication, unlike the partial reduplication found in the Madurese language. Minangkabau reduplication can be categorized into three types: complete reduplication, sound-altering reduplication, and reduplication with affixation. Words that can be reduplicated in Minangkabau include nouns, verbs, adjectives, numerals, pronouns, and particles. Here is a detailed explanation of each type.

a) Complete Reduplication

The first form of reduplication in Minangkabau is complete reduplication. This morphological process involves fully repeating the base form of a word without any addition, omission, or alteration. This form of reduplication is the most common, and many words can be formed through complete reduplication. Generally, these words belong to the classes of nouns, verbs, adjectives, numerals, pronouns, and particles. Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>pituluik</i>	<i>pituluik-pituluik</i>	pencils
<i>duduak</i>	<i>duduak-duduak</i>	sitting around
<i>manih</i>	<i>manih-manih</i>	sweet things
<i>tigo</i>	<i>tigo-tigo</i>	three of each
<i>iko</i>	<i>iko-iko</i>	these things
<i>alun</i>	<i>alun-alun</i>	not yet

b) Sound-Altering Reduplication

The second form of reduplication in Minangkabau is sound-altering reduplication, where the phonemes of the base word change during the reduplication process. These phonemes can be either vowels or consonants. This form of reduplication is similar to that found in the Indonesian language, and some lexical items have even been borrowed into Indonesian. Words that undergo sound-altering reduplication typically belong to specific nouns, verbs, and adjectives. Examples of repetitions changing vowel sounds:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>campiang</i>	<i>compang-campiang</i>	ragged
<i>baliak</i>	<i>bolak-baliak</i>	back and forth
<i>kutak</i>	<i>kutak-katiak</i>	shaking repeatedly
<i>garak</i>	<i>garak-garik</i>	movements

Examples of repetitions changing consonant sounds:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>iruak</i>	<i>iruak-pikuak</i>	bustling
<i>coreang</i>	<i>coreang-moreang</i>	smudged
<i>ereng</i>	<i>ereng-gendeng</i>	deviant actions

<i>anak</i>	<i>anak-pinak</i>	descendants
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c) Reduplication with Affixation

The third form of reduplication in Minangkabau involves the addition of affixes. The types of affixes used in this case include i) prefixes, ii) infixes, iii) suffixes, iv) confixes, and v) mixed affixes.

i) Reduplication with Prefixes

Prefixes used in Minangkabau reduplication include *ba₁-*, *ba₂-*, *maN-*, *di-*, *ta-*, *maN+pa-*, *paN-*, *ka-*, and *sa-*. The prefix *ba-* is divided into two types in Minangkabau: *ba₁-*, which functions as an intransitive marker, and *ba₂-*, which functions as a passive marker. Basic words that can be formed into reduplicates with these prefixes are described in the following table.

Prefixes	Basic Words					
	Noun	Verb	Adjective	Numeral	Pronoun	Particle
<i>ba₁-</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>ba₂-</i>		✓				
<i>maN-</i>	✓	✓	✓			
<i>di-</i>		✓				
<i>ta-</i>	✓	✓	✓			
<i>maN+pa-</i>	✓		✓			
<i>paN-</i>	✓	✓	✓		✓	
<i>ka-</i>				✓		
<i>sa-</i>	✓		✓			

Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>lari</i>	<i>balari-lari</i>	running around
<i>ambiak</i>	<i>baambiak-ambiak</i>	taken repeatedly
<i>baco</i>	<i>mambaco-baco</i>	reading repeatedly
<i>bao</i>	<i>dibao-bao</i>	carried around
<i>jago</i>	<i>tajago-jago</i>	waking up repeatedly
<i>gadang</i>	<i>mampagadang-gadang</i>	enlarging repeatedly
<i>tinggi</i>	<i>paninggi-ninggi</i>	heightening repeatedly
<i>duo</i>	<i>kaduo-duo</i>	each of the two
<i>rancak</i>	<i>sarancak-rancak</i>	very beautiful

ii) Reduplication with Infixes

Infixes used in Minangkabau reduplication include *-ba-* and *-maN-*. Words that can undergo reduplication with these infixes come from the classes of nouns and verbs. Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>kaik</i>	<i>kaik-bakaik</i>	relating each other
<i>kaja</i>	<i>kaja-bakaja</i>	chasing each other
<i>undang</i>	<i>undang-maundang</i>	inviting repeatedly
<i>ago</i>	<i>ago-maago</i>	bargaining repeatedly

iii) Reduplication with Suffixes

Suffixes used in Minangkabau reduplication include $-an_1$ and $-an_2$. In Minangkabau, $-an_1$ functions as a noun marker, while $-an_2$ functions as a verb marker. However, both suffixes have the same form when added to reduplications. Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>makan</i>	<i>makan-makanan</i>	food
<i>untuang</i>	<i>untuang-untuangan</i>	good luck
<i>kaja</i>	<i>kaja-kajaan</i>	chasing each other

iv) Reduplication with Confixes

Confixes used in Minangkabau reduplication include ba_1-an_2 , ba_2-an_2 , ba_2-i , $maN-an_2$, $maN-i$, $di-i$, $di-an_2$, $ta-i$, $ta-an_2$, $maN+pa-an_2$, $maN+pa-i$, and $ka-an_2$. Basic words that can be formed into reduplications with these confixes are described in the following table.

Confixes	Basic Words					
	Noun	Verb	Adjective	Numeral	Pronoun	Particle
ba_1-an_2	✓	✓	✓		✓	
ba_2-an_2		✓				
ba_2-i	✓	✓	✓			
$maN-an_2$	✓	✓	✓	✓		
$maN-i$	✓	✓	✓			
$di-i$	✓	✓	✓			
$di-an_2$		✓				
$ta-i$	✓	✓	✓			
$ta-an_2$	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
$maN+pa-an_2$	✓	✓	✓	✓		
$maN+pa-i$	✓	✓	✓		✓	
$ka-an_2$	✓		✓			

Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>paneh</i>	<i>bapaneh-panehan</i>	heated repeatedly
<i>bali</i>	<i>babali-balian</i>	bought repeatedly
<i>naiak</i>	<i>banaiak-naiaki</i>	ascended repeatedly
<i>iyo</i>	<i>maiyo-iyoan</i>	affirming repeatedly
<i>minyak</i>	<i>maminyak-minyaki</i>	greasing repeatedly
<i>camin</i>	<i>dicamin-camini</i>	reflected repeatedly
<i>bali</i>	<i>dibali-balian</i>	bought repeatedly
<i>lubang</i>	<i>talubang-lubangi</i>	punctured repeatedly
<i>jalan</i>	<i>tajalan-jalanan</i>	walking repeatedly
<i>elo</i>	<i>mampaelo-eloan</i>	attracting repeatedly
<i>salang</i>	<i>mampasalang-salangi</i>	borrowing repeatedly
<i>batino</i>	<i>kabatino-batinoan</i>	femininity

v) Reduplication with Mixed Affixes

Mixed affixes used in Minangkabau reduplication include combinations of the infix $-maN-$ and the suffix $-i$. Words that can undergo reduplication with these mixed affixes come from the classes of nouns, verbs, and adjectives. Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>guru</i>	<i>guru-mangguri</i>	teaching each other

<i>dakek</i>	<i>dakek-mandakeki</i>	approaching each other
<i>janguak</i>	<i>janguak-manjanguaki</i>	visiting each other

Additionally, reduplication with a combination of infix *-maN-* and suffix *-an₂* is also found. Words that can undergo this form of reduplication are typically verbs. Examples:

Basic Word	Reduplicated Form	Meaning
<i>cibia</i>	<i>cibia-mancibiaan</i>	sneering at each other
<i>tungok</i>	<i>tungok-manungokan</i>	pushing each other

D. The Meaning of Minangkabau Reduplication

The form of reduplication in Minangkabau are highly varied or complex. This can be seen from the various affixes that can be added to Minangkabau reduplication as above. Reduplication in Minangkabau also has various meanings, namely as follows.

a) Plural Meaning

The first meaning of reduplication is to indicate plurality. This reduplication meaning applies to the repetition of nouns, adjectives, verbs, pronouns, and numerals with the following conditions. (a) For noun class repetition: i) full repetition such as *rumah-rumah* ('houses'); ii) repetition with the insertion of morphemes *-ka-* and *sajo*, such as *pitih-ka-pitih sajo* ('always just money'); iii) sound-changing repetition such as *lauak-pauak* ('various dishes'); iv) repetition with the addition of the prefix *pa-* such as *padagang-padagang* ('traders'); v) repetition with the addition of the confix *pa-an₁* such as *pangatahuan-pangatahuan* ('pieces of knowledge'); vi) repetition with the addition of the prefix *ka-* such as *kakasiah-kakasiah* ('lovers'); vii) repetition with the addition of the confix *ka-an₂* such as *kapandaian-kapandaian* ('skills'); and viii) repetition with the addition of the suffix *-an₁* or *-an₂* such as *buah-buahan* ('fruits') and *masakan-masakan* ('dishes').

(b) For adjective class repetition: i) full repetition such as *ijau-ijau* ('greenish'); ii) repetition with the insertion of morphemes *-ka-* and *sajo* such as *sakik-ka-sakik sajo* ('only hurts'). (c) For verb class repetition: i) full repetition such as *lalok-lalok* ('sleeping'); ii) repetition with the insertion of morphemes *-ka-* and *sajo* such as *pai-ka-pai sajo* ('going just to go'); iii) sound-changing repetition such as *bulak-baliak* ('back and forth'); iv) repetition with the addition of the prefix *maN-* such as *mamanciang-mamanciang* ('fishing'); v) repetition with the addition of the prefix *ba-* such as *bacakak-bacakak* ('fighting'); vi) repetition with the addition of the prefix *ta-* such as *takunyah-takunyah* ('chewing'); vii) repetition with the addition of the prefix *di-* such as *dibae-dibae* ('throwing repeatedly').

(d) For pronoun class repetition, the repetition is always in full form. This condition only applies to personal pronouns, demonstratives, and interrogatives such as *kami-kami* ('we'), *itu-itu* ('those'), and *sia-sia* ('who'). (e) For numeral class repetition, it is in full form. This condition only applies to numerals indicating the number one, such as *ciek-ciek* ('one by one'). However, not all repetitions of the numeral *ciek* imply plurality. In some contexts, it may even mean 'a few'. To distinguish this, one must consider the context of the sentence. Meanwhile, numerals indicating a number greater than one cannot be reduplicated, as these words already imply plurality without reduplication.

b) Repetition

The second meaning of reduplication is to indicate actions that are repeated continuously within the same period. This reduplication meaning applies to the repetition of specific verbs with the conditions: (a) addition of the prefix *maN-* such as *manokok-nokok* ('repeatedly hitting') and *mamakiak-makiak* ('shrieking'); and (b) addition of the confix *maN-an₂* such as *maanguak-anguakkan* ('nodding repeatedly').

c) Reciprocal

The third meaning of reduplication is to describe activities that involve mutual action or reciprocity. This reduplication meaning applies to the repetition of specific verbs that denote

actions performed by humans or animals, with the conditions: (a) addition of the infix *-maN-* such as *paguik-mamaguik* ('hugging each other'); (b) addition of a mixed affix, namely the infix *-maN-* plus the suffix *-i*, such as *kunjuang-manujuangi* ('visiting each other'); (c) addition of a mixed affix, namely the infix *-maN-* plus *-an₂*, such as *cibia-mancibiaan* ('sneering at each other'); (d) addition of the infix *-ba₁-* such as *sauik-basauik* ('responding to each other'); and (e) addition of the confix *ba-an₂* such as *balokok-lokokan* ('hitting each other').

d) Emphasis

The fourth meaning of reduplication is to emphasize the repeated word. This reduplication meaning applies to verbs, nouns, and adjectives with perfect repetition or sound-changing repetition, such as *datang-datang* ('coming repeatedly'), *batu-batu* ('stones'), *rancak-rancak* ('very nice'), *puntang-pantiang* ('all over the place'), and *carai-barai* ('scattered'). Moreover, this reduplication meaning also applies to adjectives with perfect repetition with the addition of: (a) enclitic *-nyo* such as *lamak-lamaknyo* ('deliciously'); (b) prefix *ba-* such as *bagadang-gadang* ('greatly large'); (c) prefix *sa-* such as *sajauah-jauah* ('as far as'); (d) prefix *sa-* plus enclitic *-nyo* such as *sarancak-rancaknyo* ('as beautiful as'); (e) suffix *-an* such as *mati-matian* ('with all effort'). Furthermore, this reduplication meaning also applies to nouns with the addition of the confix *sa-an₁* such as *samalam-malaman* ('all night long') and *sapakan-pakanan* ('every week').

e) Weakening Attribute

The fifth meaning of reduplication is to weaken the attribute of a word. This reduplication meaning applies to perfect repetitions of adjectives such as *malu-malu* ('somewhat shy') and *paniang-paniang* ('somewhat dizzy'). This reduplication meaning also applies to certain nouns or adjectives repeated with the confix *ka-an₁* such as *kapadusi-padusian* ('somewhat womanly') and *kaijau-ijauan* ('somewhat greenish').

f) Indicating Fun or Playfulness

The sixth meaning of reduplication is to indicate something done for enjoyment. This reduplication meaning applies to intransitive verbs that are reduplicated by: (a) full repetition such as *mandi-mandi* ('bathing for fun'); (b) repetition with the addition of the prefix *ba-* such as *baranang-ranang* ('swimming leisurely'); (c) repetition with the addition of the prefix *maN-* such as *mambaco-baco* ('reading for fun'); (d) repetition with the addition of the prefix *paN-* such as *paisi-isi paruik* ('snacking'). This reduplication meaning also applies to nouns with perfect repetition such as *baeko-baeko* ('delaying for fun').

g) Resemblance to Something

The seventh meaning of reduplication is to indicate resemblance to something. This reduplication meaning applies to nouns, either repeated perfectly such as *rumah-rumah* ('toy houses') and *gulo-gulo* ('candy'), or repeated with the addition of the suffix *-an₁* such as *dotor-dotoran* ('pretend doctors') and *oto-otoan* ('toy cars').

h) Distributive

The eighth meaning of reduplication is to indicate distribution. This relates to quantity or measurement. Therefore, this reduplication meaning applies to numerals with perfect repetition, such as *duo-duo* ('in pairs') and *tigo-tigo* ('in threes'). Moreover, this reduplication meaning also applies to noun repetitions with the addition of the prefixes *sa-* and *ba-* such as *salangkah-salangkah* ('step by step') and *barampek-barampek* ('in fours').

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the contrastive analysis presented above, it can be concluded that there are similarities and differences in the forms and meanings of reduplication in the Madurese and Minangkabau languages. The similarities include the presence of sound-altering reduplication and reduplication with affixation in both languages. Additionally, there are five shared meanings of reduplication in both languages: plurality, imitation, repeated actions, reciprocal actions, and expressing something done for fun or playfulness.

The differences in the form and meaning of reduplication in Madurese and Minangkabau are as follows. (a) The form of reduplication in Madurese is in the form of partial repetition, while in Minangkabau it is in the form of complete repetition. (b) Words that can be reduplicatable in Madurese come from the noun, verb, adjective, and numeral classes, while in Minangkabau they come from the noun, verb, adjective, numeral, pronoun, and particle classes. (c) Reduplication with the addition of affixes in Minangkabau is more diverse than in Madurese. (d) The meanings resulting from the reduplication process in Madurese are found to have 12 variations of meaning and 1 other is meaningless or merely a variation of language style, while in Minangkabau 8 variations of meaning are found. The meanings of reduplication in Madurese that are not found in Minangkabau are pretending; a tool for doing something; hope; commanding; superlative meaning; pointing to an object; and an expression of surprise. The meaning of reduplication in Minangkabau language that is not found in Madurese language is emphasis; weakening of character; and distributive.

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